

River Research Institute

ISSN 1606-9277

TECHNICAL JOURNAL

Vol. 12

No. 01

June 2014

RIVER RESEARCH INSTITUTE

FARIDPUR, BANGLADESH

TECHNICAL
JOURNAL

Vol. 12 No. 01 June 2014

RIVER RESEARCH INSTITUTE
FARIDPUR, BANGLADESH

**TECHNICAL JOURNAL
RIVER RESEARCH INSTITUTE, FARIDPUR**

Vol. 12, No. 01, June 2014

CONTENTS

SI. No.	Title of the Paper with Author's Name	Page
1.	Land Reclamation in Char Islands of Bangladesh Using Mathematical Modelling Tool: A Case Study on Char Mainka-Montaz Area Mohammad Ziaur Rahman, Golam Mohiuddin and Zahirul Haque Khan	1
2.	Depleting Trend of Fresh Water Resources with Increase in Water Use is a Threat in Bogra District: A Case Study Muhammad Abdullah	15
3.	The Best Canal Lining Technology: A Review Syed Md. Anwaruzzaman, Uma Saha, Md. Abul Ala Moududi and Md. Zubayerul Islam	27
4.	Sustainable Water Resources Management Through Mathematical Modelling for North West Region of Bangladesh Md. Tarikul Islam and Dr. AFM Afzal Hossain, PEng.	32
5.	Groundwater Utilization in Irrigation Business: A Field Study in Ghatail Thana of Tangail District Md. Alauddin Hossain, Mohammad Raju Ahmed, Md. Abul Ala Moududi and Md. Azam Khan	44
6.	Physical Modelling for Refinement and Verification of Hydraulic Design of Gorai Off-take Interventions Pintu Kanungoe, Md. Abul Ala Moududi, Md. Johurul Islam, Md. Azizul Haque Podder and Shailen Kumer Ghosh	55

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper with Author's Name	Page
7.	Laboratory Study on Channel Routing Alal Uddin, Rubaed Foysal Al Masum, Md. Moniruzzaman and Md. Zubayerul Islam	68
8.	Analytical Explanation of Riverbank Failure Mechanisms Aysha Akter	80
9.	Sustainability of an Artificial Dredged Channel Along the Braided Jamuna River of Bangladesh Md. Mosiur Rahman, Nishan Kumar Biswas, Shovon Jubair and Md. Munsur Rahman!	92
10.	Sediment Budget of Meghna Estuary Mohammad Ziaur Rahman, Md. Nazmul Azim Beg And Zahirul Haque Khan	106
11.	Optimization of Bank Protection Works by Physical Modelling for the Protection of Kushtia Town at Right Bank of Gorai River Swapan Kumar Das, A.K.M.Ashrafuzzaman and Md. Abul Ala Moududi	119
12.	Determination of Design Parameters for Revetment Using Physical Modelling: A Case Study A.K.M.Ashrafuzzaman, Md. Rafiqul Alam, Md. Azizul Haque Podder and Md. Alauddin Hossain	131
13	River Bank Erosion Impact on Socio-economic Condition: A Field Study in Banaripara Upazilla of Barisal District Md. Zubayerul Islam, Md. Alauddin Hossain, Dibakar Chakma, Md. Mehedi Hasan and Alal Uddin	146
14.	Modelling of Clusters using Artificial Neural Network A.K.M.Ashrafuzzaman, Md. Rafiqul Alam and Pintu Kanungoe	157

SEDIMENT BUDGET OF MEGHNA ESTUARY

Mohammad Ziaur Rahman¹, Md. Nazmul Azim Beg², Zahirul Haque Khan³

Abstract

Bangladesh is the largest delta of the world formed mainly by alluvial deposit of the Ganges, the Brahmaputra and the Meghna river systems. These three mighty rivers carry annually more than a billion tons of total sediment. The sediment load is then conveyed by Lower Meghna River and discharged into the Bay of Bengal. The river borne sediment inflow from the three major rivers the Ganges, the Brahmaputra and the Meghna influences the morphological development of the Meghna Estuary. Analysis of time series bathymetric chart collected under different project over the years has been done to analyze the spatial distribution of sediment deposition and erosion. The Natural Neighbour method is used for interpolation of surveyed data to develop sea bed topography using Mike 21 FM. The entire area has been divided into seven sub areas and erosion/ deposition volumes have been calculated based on interpolated depth values of the maps using 50x50m grid. The analysis of bathymetric data shows that accretion process exceeds the erosion process in the Meghna Estuary. Erosion process is dominant in the upper region of the estuary part i.e. from Chandpur to north of Bhola island, north coast of Hatiya island and northeast coast of Bhola and along the Boyer char (Ramgati). The highest rate of deposition is seen in the Sandwip, Jahajerchar and Urirchar area. The net deposition of sediment over the last ten years (1999 to 20098) in the entire estuary is about 2,760 Mm³ and annual average is about 276 Mm³.

Introduction

The alluvial deposits of the Ganges, Brahmaputra and Meghna rivers formed Bangladesh, the largest delta of the world. These three mighty rivers drain an area of about 1.72 million sq km, of which only about 7% lies within Bangladesh, and finally empties to the Bay of Bengal through Lower Meghna Estuary. The Ganges River drains a catchment of 1,114,000 km² and the Brahmaputra River a catchment of 935,000 km², supplying in combination around a billion tonnes of sediment each year to the Bengal Basin. Delta plains exceed 115,000 km² in surface area (Woodroffe *et al.*, 2006), comprising the Meghna Delta plain (built by the two rivers downstream of their confluence) to the east, and an abandoned delta plain, the Gangetic Tidal plain to the west. Annually about 1250 billion cubic meters (BCM) of trans-boundary flow drains through Bangladesh to the estuary carrying about 1.1 billion tons of suspended sediment (O'Connor, and Nicholson, 1989). The coast along the Meghna River estuary is very dynamic with rapid erosion and accretion. The Ganges-Brahmaputra system carries about 1 billion tonnes of sediment each year (Allison, 1998a, Islam *et al.*, 1999). About 30% of the modern sediment is distributed in the delta plain (Goodbred and Kuehl, 1998), 21% along the topset of the subaqueous delta (Allison, 1998b), 20% along the foreset of the subaqueous delta (Michels *et al.*, 1998) and the rest 29% is carried to the Swatch of No Ground (Goodbred and Kuehl, 1999).

¹Junior Specialist, Coast Port and Estuary Management Division, IWM, email: zia@iwmbd.org; ²Junior Specialist, Coast Port and Estuary Management Division, IWM, email: nab@iwmbd.org; ³Director and Principal Specialist, Coast Port and Estuary Management Division, IWM, email: zhk@iwmbd.org.

Land accretion and erosion in the Meghna Estuary is a continuous and gradual natural process. The net average annual natural accretion is quite significant in the estuary ranging 1200 ha/y to 1900 ha/y (MES, 2001). The sediment load is then conveyed by Lower Meghna River and discharged into the Bay of Bengal. The main sources of sediment for land accretion are sediment carried by upland rivers, erosion from char and the shelf. The river borne sediment inflow from the three major rivers Ganges, Brahmaputra and Meghna influences the morphological development of the Meghna Estuary. Factors that play major role on accretion and erosion are the sediment load, its transport and distribution, the discharge of water, tidal forces and estuarine circulation (IWM, 2010).

The knowledge on sediment deposition volume and its distribution in the Meghna estuary is limited. It is important to know how much sediment is retained in the Meghna estuary and distribution of sediment deposition and erosion for understanding the morphological developments and planning of land reclamation and erosion control (Kamal *et al.*, 2012). This objective of this paper is to assess the erosion-deposition pattern in the Meghna estuary.

Approach & Methodology

The study mainly focuses on the processes of river and estuarine hydraulics and the erosion-deposition pattern of the Meghna Estuary. The modelling study has been devised in combination with data analysis and numerical modelling. The two dimensional (2-D) flexible mesh model (MIKE21 FM) has been applied for hydro-morphological investigation around the study area. Data on recent bathymetry, sediment concentration and hydrometrics of the estuary have been utilized for updating and re-calibrating the existing Bay of Bengal model.

Data Collection

The Bay of Bengal model is updated with the primary data surveyed in the year 2009 and the secondary data collected from different agencies. A survey team comprising of SSSU of EDP, SSD and SUA of BWDB surveyed the bathymetry of the Meghna Estuary, water level, discharge and sediment concentration data in 2009-2010.

Figure 1: Bathymetric data collected under different cruises of EDP in 2009-2010

The transect lines of bathymetry survey of BWDB and IWM survey teams are shown in Figure 1 and 2, respectively.

Figure 2: River/ channel cross section survey in the Tentulia River and Char

Montaz Area

Data surveyed under previous studies have been collected and compiled. Table 1 presents the list of data collected under past studies.

Table 1: List of data collected from secondary sources

Data	Source	Name of Study	Period
Bathymetry	BWDB	Land Reclamation Project	1983
do	BWDB	Meghna Estuary Study II	2000
do	BWDB	Feasibility Study for Haitya-Nijhum Dwip Cross Dam Project	2006
do	CDSP III	Survey and Modelling Study of Sandwip-Urirchar-Noakhali Cross-Dam(s)	2008
Water Level	CDSP III	Survey and Modelling Study of Sandwip-Urirchar-Noakhali Cross-Dam(s)	2008
do	BIWTA	-	2001-2009
Discharge	CDSP III	Survey and Modelling Study of Sandwip-Urirchar-Noakhali Cross-Dam(s)	2008
Wind	BMD	-	1948-2008

Data Analysis

The bathymetry data over the entire Meghna Estuary was surveyed and the data has been analysed. The data quality has been checked comparing upstream and downstream data in same location. BWDB checked the consistency of Bench Mark values that were used in bathymetric survey and corrected the bathymetry accordingly. The bathymetric map thus generated from surveyed data is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Updated bathymetry based on recent survey data

Model Development

Hydrodynamic Model

In this study the existing Bay of Bengal model has been updated with the surveyed hydro-morphological data and latest satellite imagery using MIKE 21FM modelling system. The model domain extends from Chandpur in the Lower Meghna river to in the north, to about 16° Latitude in the Bay of Bengal in the south. The coverage of the numerical model is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Bathymetry of the Bay of Bengal (with triangular flexible mesh) where color gradient shows the sea bed level in mPWD datum

There are two open boundaries in the model, one is in the Lower Meghna River at Chandpur (northern boundary) and the one is in the Bay of Bengal (southern boundary). Predicted tide has been used in the southern boundary and observed water level at Chandpur BIWTA Station has been used in the northern boundary.

The riverbank alignment (land boundary) in the northern part of the model has been updated on the basis of the mosaic of IRS P6 LISS III satellite image 2008 provided by EDP. The model applies PWD datum. The southern part of the Bay of Bengal is quite deep and the maximum depth along the southern open boundary is more than 3,000 meter. The computational grid or mesh size decreases (or the resolution increases) towards coastlines and Islands. Inter-tidal areas are flooded and dried during a tidal cycle, both in nature and in the model.

Sediment Transport Model

The cohesive sediment transport module is coupled to the hydrodynamic module and they run in parallel. The governing equation for sediment transport is solved in the same mesh and applies information of water levels and currents from the hydrodynamic module to calculate the sediment transport. One layer describes the sea bed in the sediment transport model. At the upstream boundary in the Lower Meghna River, suspended sediment concentration time-series has been applied based on past measurements. Zero sediment concentration has been assumed at the south boundary. Initial sediment concentration in the Meghna Estuary is also based on the field measurement by IWM and MES measurement.

The governing equations used in MIKE21 in solving hydraulic problems in coastal areas are:

Conservation of mass equation

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial q}{\partial y} = 0; \quad (1)$$

Conservation of momentum equation

The momentum equation in the x-direction is given by:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial p^2}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial pq}{\partial y} + gh \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x} + \frac{f}{2} \frac{\sqrt{p^2 + q^2}}{h^2} p - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \tau_{xy} h}{\partial y} - \Omega q - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho} C_w W W_x + \frac{h}{\rho} \frac{\partial p_a}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (2a)$$

The momentum equation in the y-direction is given by:

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial q^2}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial pq}{\partial x} + gh \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial y} + \frac{f}{2} \frac{\sqrt{p^2 + q^2}}{h^2} q - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \tau_{yx} h}{\partial x} + \Omega p - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho} C_w W W_y + \frac{h}{\rho} \frac{\partial p_a}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (2b)$$

Where,

- p and q flux in x and y directions respectively (m³/s/m)
- t time (s), x and y (m) are Cartesian Co-ordinate (s)
- h water depth (m)
- g acceleration due to gravity (9.81 m²/s)
- ε sea surface elevation (m)
- ρ_w & ρ_a air and water density respectively (kg /m³)
- C_w wind friction factor = 0.0008 + 0.000065W in accordance with Wu (1982)
- W wind speed (m/s)
- Ω Coriolis parameter =5.2*10⁻⁵ s⁻¹ in the Bay of Bengal
- P_a atmospheric pressure (kg/m²s²)

Model Calibration

The updated two-dimensional hydrodynamic and sediment transport models of the Bay of Bengal have been calibrated against water level, discharge and suspended sediment concentration at different locations comparing the model results with field measurement to make the model performance to a satisfactory level. The validation has been made only with the available data for the year 2008. Data was collected for monsoon in 2009 and dry season in 2010. Locations of calibration areas have been presented in Figure 5 and some calibration plots in Figure 6 to 8.

Figure 5: Calibration locations of Bay of Bengal Model

Figure 6: Calibration results of Bay of Bengal Model on water level

Figure 7: Calibration results of Bay of Bengal Model on discharge

Figure 8: Calibration results of Bay of Bengal Model on suspended sediment concentration

Sediment Transport Process

Erosion

The erosion rate is a function of stream power, whereas sedimentation rate is a function of suspended sediment concentration (SSC), settling velocity of sediment particles or sediment flocks and local velocity field. The erosion of a bed layer is the transfer of sediment from the bed to the water column. Erosion takes place from the active bed layer in areas where the bed shear stress (τ_b) is larger than the critical shear stress for erosion (τ_{ce}). For dense consolidated bed the erosion rate for the j 'th layer is described as (Partheniades, 1989):

For soft, partly consolidated bed the erosion rate for the j 'th layer is described as (Parchure & Mehta, 1985):

$$E^j = E_0^j P_E^j E_m^j$$

Where P_E^j is a probability ramp function of erosion, E_0 is erosion coefficient, E_m is the power of erosion, α is a coefficient, τ_{ce} is critical shear stress for erosion and τ_b is bed shear stress.

$$E = E_0^j \exp(\alpha(\tau_b - \tau_{ce}^j))$$

The Probability ramp function of erosion is defined as:

$$p_E^j = \max\left(0, \frac{\tau_b}{\tau_{ce}^i} - 1\right)$$

Deposition

The deposition of suspended sediment is the transfer of sediment from the water column to the bed. Deposition takes places where the bed shear stress (τ_b) is smaller than the critical shear stress for deposition (τ_{cd}). The deposition for the i 'th mud fraction is described as (Krone, 1962):

$$D^i = w_s^i c_b^i p_D^i$$

Where P_D^i is a Probability ramp function of deposition, W_s is the fall velocity and c_b is the near bed concentration of fraction i .

The Probability ramp function of deposition is defined as:

$$p_D^i = \max\left(0, \min\left(1, 1 - \frac{\tau_b}{\tau_{cd}^i}\right)\right)$$

Sediment concentration during spring tide than that of during neap tide is always higher and the concentration also varies from monsoon to dry season. The field measurements in the Sandwip area show that sediment concentration during spring tide is about 4 to 10 times higher than that of neap tide (IWM, 2010). The major parts of the suspended sediment comprises of very fine sand and silt. The median bed-material grain size varies from 16 to 250 μm (MES, 2001). The sediment transport model provides the erosion deposition pattern in the estuary, which is found similar to the field conditions based on bathymetric survey i.e. location of erosion and deposition are more or less same though magnitude is different to some extent. The simulation results also include sediment transport through the lower Meghna River and the net sediment transport.

The upland sediment carried by river is trapped in the estuary by tidal pumping and residual circulation and mixed with the sediment brought from the continental shelf. The mixing process leads to continuous deposition and erosion and exchange of sediment in the estuary. More sediment measurements during monsoon and dry seasons are needed to enhance the understanding of accretion and erosion process and distribution of sediment deposition.

Figure 9: Simulated Bathymetry at present condition (Left) and after three years (Right).

Sediment Budget & Land Erosion-Accretion in the Estuary

Analysis of time series bathymetric chart collected under different project over the years has been made to assess the spatial distribution of sediment deposition and erosion. The Natural Neighbour method is used for interpolation of surveyed data to develop sea bed topography. The bathymetric chart based on the surveyed data under EDP in 2009-10 has been compared with that of 1999-2000 under MES II study to estimate erosion and deposition volume in the Meghna estuary. In the Sandwip-Urirchar-Noakhali area, bathymetric data surveyed by IWM in 2008 under CDSP III project have been compared with the bathymetric data of 1999 collected under MES II.

The entire study area was divided into seven sub-areas delineated in the MES II study. In each sub-area bathymetric maps have been prepared for both 1999 and 2009 data using MIKE 21. The overall difference of bathymetry map for the seven sub-areas is presented in Figure 10. Erosion and deposition volumes have been calculated based on interpolated depth values of the maps using 50x50m grid squares.

Figure 10: Bed level changes in seven sub-areas of Meghna Estuary (1999-2009)

Sediment budget calculations identify sediment sources and sinks in a delta system and allow predictions of how changes to the rate of sediment import or export might be reflected in a delta's construction or deconstruction (Kimberly et al., 2013). After analysing of bathymetric data from 1999-2009 (Figure 10) and 3 years morphological simulation (Figure 9) it can conclude that erosion process is dominant in the upper region of the estuary part i.e. from Chandpur to north of Bhola island, north coast of Hatiya Island and northeast coast of Bhola and along the Boyer char (Ramgati). The analysis of bathymetric data shows that accretion process exceeds the erosion process in the Meghna Estuary. The net deposition of sediment over the last ten years period in the entire estuary was about 0.05 m/year. The highest rate of deposition (0.22m/year) is seen in the Sandwip-Urirchar region. The erosion and deposition volumes estimated for the sub-areas are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Net change of sediment volume in the Meghna Estuary

Sub area	Erosion		Deposition		Net Deposition			Net Change
	Volume (Mm ³)	Area (ha)	Volume (Mm ³)	Area (ha)	Volume (Mm ³)	Volume (Mm ³ /yr)	Total Area (ha)	m/yr
A1	1467	27411	892	23694	-574	-57	51105	-0.11
A2	2050	45400	1908	44707	-142	-14	90107	-0.02
A3	1408	64956	1941	93801	533	53	158756	0.03
A4	366	16838	1594	44758	1228	136 ¹⁾	61596	0.22
A5	547	25934	1492	60422	944	94	86356	0.11
A6	672	35516	1138	59376	465	47	94892	0.05
A7	139	13383	444	34104	305	31	47487	0.06
Total	6649	229438	9409	360860	2760	276	590298	0.05

1) The yearly change has been estimated dividing the total change by 9 years because 2008 survey was used instead of 2009 survey.

Conclusions

The analysis of bathymetric data shows that accretion process exceeds the erosion process in the Meghna Estuary. Erosion process is dominant in the upper region of the estuary part i.e. from Chandpur to north of Bhola island, north coast of Hatiya island and northeast coast of Bhola and along the Boyer char (Ramgati). The highest rate of deposition is seen in the Sandwip, Jahajerchar and Urirchar area. The net deposition of sediment over the last ten years period in the entire estuary is about 2,760 Mm³ and annual average is about 276 Mm³, which is very high compared to a similar analysis done under MES II study. In MES II study about 300 Mm³ deposition was found in three years in the estuary. The remarkable difference with the MES analysis is in area 5, where present study shows huge net deposition of sediment instead of erosion as found in the MES II. It is essential to establish consistent bench mark in the estuary and to continue the bathymetric survey of the entire estuary for better understanding of the morphological processes and identification of potential location for land reclamation.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their deepest gratitude to the Institute of Water Modelling (IWM), Bangladesh Water Development Board (BWDB), Meghna Estuary Survey (MES) team for the support to use their study findings in the paper. They also thankful to Danish Hydraulic Institute (DHI) for using MIKE 21FM Modelling tool.

References

- Allison MA 1998a. Geologic framework and environmental status of the Ganges-Brahmaputra delta. *J Coastal Res* 14: 826-836.
- Allison MA 1998b. Historical changes in the Ganges-Brahmaputra delta front. *J Coastal Res* 14: 1269-1275.
- Goodbred S.L., Kuehl S.A. 1998. Floodplain processes in the Bengal Basin and the storage of Ganges-Brahmaputra river sediment: an accretion study using ^{137}Cs and ^{210}Pb geochronology. *Sediment Geol* 121: 239-258.
- Goodbred S.L., Kuehl S.A. 1999. Holocene and modern sediment budgets for the Ganges-Brahmaputra river system: evidence for highstand dispersal to flood-plain, shelf, and deep-sea depocenters. *Geol* 27: 559-562.
- Islam M.R., Begum S.F., Yamaguchi Y, Ogawa K. 1999. The Ganges and Brahmaputra Rivers in Bangladesh: basin denudation and sedimentation. *Hydrol Process* 13: 2907-2923
- IWM 2010. Updating of Hydrodynamic & Morphological Models to Investigate Land Accretion & Erosion in the Estuary Development Program (EDP) Area.
- Kamal. F. A., Ahmed. M. M. Z., Rahman. M. Z. and Khan. Z. H. 2012. Land Reclamation Potentials in the Meghna Estuary, COPEDEC 2012, IIT Madras, Chennai, INDIA. 20-24 Feb. 2012.
- Kimberly G. Rogers., Steven L. Goodbred Jr., Dhiman R. Mondal. 2013. Monsoon sedimentation on the 'abandoned' tide-influenced Ganges Brahmaputra delta plain, Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science 131 (2013) 297-309.
- MES 2001. MES-II, Meghna Estuary Study, Hydro-morphological Dynamics of the Meghna Estuary.
- Michels K.H, Kudrass H.R, Hübscher C, Suckow A, Wiedicke M. 1998. The submarine delta of the Ganges-Brahmaputra: cyclone-dominated sedimentation patterns. *Mar Geol* 149:133-154.
- O'Connor, B.A. and Nicholson J. 1989. Modelling changes in coastal morphology. *Proc. A.S.C.E. Int. Symposium on Sediment Transport Modelling*, S.Y. Wang (Ed.), pp. 160165.
- Woodroffe C.D., Nicholls R.J., Saito Y, Chen Z, Goodbred S.L. 2006. Landscape Variability and the Response of Asian Megadeltas to Environmental Change: The Asia-Pacific Region. In Harvey N, *Global Change and Integrated Coastal Management*, Springer, The Netherlands pp. 277-314.